

HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF PILGRIMAGE TOURISM

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564306>

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Annotation: *This article describes the history and stages of development of pilgrimage tourism.*

Keywords: *pilgrimage tourism, religious tourism, history of pilgrimage tourism*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada ziyorat turizmi tarixi va rivojlanish bosqichlari yoritilgan.*

Kalit soʻzlar: *ziyosat turizmi, diniy turizm, ziyosat turizmi tarixi*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассказывается об истории и этапах развития паломнического туризма.*

Ключевые слова: *паломнический туризм, религиозный туризм, история паломнического туризма.*

Introduction. Pilgrimage - walking or traveling to holy places with well-defined cult purposes. Pilgrimage in one form or another is accepted in almost all religions and pagan cults. At present, pilgrims widely use the services of the tourism industry, special travel companies are being created to organize such tours. Pilgrimage tours, in contrast to religious-educational or cultural-historical ones, carry a certain belief in the meaning of the ritual, and not just educational goals. The entertainment section of the program has been significantly reduced, although health and educational recreation as such is allowed.

The meaning of pilgrimage is to worship holy places. This worship is of a religious nature and is associated with the performance of divine services and prayers at revered shrines. Any other visit to holy places that is not connected with religious worship, strictly speaking, is not related to the canonical pilgrimage.

This kind of religious tourism is a combination of trips of representatives of various religions for pilgrimage purposes. We can understand a pilgrimage as a journey of people to worship holy places. Many different motives motivate people to make pilgrimages.

First, the performance of a religious rite (prayer, communion, confession). Religious ordinances are the most important inner foundation. Second, spiritual development. Tens and hundreds of thousands of different people are drawn to

the holy cloisters precisely for spiritual food. Thirdly, receiving grace, spiritual and physical advice. Fourth, religious education. Fifthly, worship of a holy place, temple, relics.

Pilgrimage is a journey to famous places of worship for the purpose of worship and participation in religious ceremonies. Pilgrimage is the oldest type of cult activity. As a rule, the pilgrimage is aimed at participation in religious rites performed in the most famous cult shrines (temples).

The term "pilgrimage", as philologists believe, comes from the word "palm tree" - the branches of this tree were brought by the first Christian pilgrims who visited the Holy Land during the holiday "Entry of the Lord into Jerusalem". During the triumphal entry of Jesus Christ into Jerusalem, believers strewed his path with palm branches. In Russia, this holiday was called "Palm Sunday".

A tourist traveling for religious purposes is a person who travels outside the usual environment for a period of not more than a year to visit holy places and centers of religions. Religious (pilgrimage) tourism should be understood as activities related to the provision of services and satisfaction of the needs of tourists traveling to holy places and religious centers that are outside their usual environment.

One of the important aspects of pilgrimages is their spiritual and educational component. When visiting holy places, people learn about the history and spiritual traditions of monasteries and temples, the features of worship, saints and ascetics of piety, whose life and work was connected with the shrines included in the pilgrimage route. Pilgrims have the opportunity to talk with the inhabitants of the monasteries, some of them find confessors here. Pilgrimage also plays an important general educational role. Monasteries and churches in Russia have always been not only a place of spiritual activity, but also cultural centers. For centuries, books, icons, works of applied art, handicrafts have accumulated here.

Mass pilgrimage became in the era of the Middle Ages. Hundreds of thousands of people went to the Middle East to touch Christian shrines. In fact, the Crusades were aimed at freeing Christian shrines from Muslims in order to make them more accessible to pilgrims. Pilgrim trips were made from the ports of France and Italy and were quite well organized. With the development of the process of secularization (the loss of the influence of the church on society), the intensity of the pilgrimage began to fall, and by the beginning of the 20th century, the mass pilgrimage had ceased. During the Soviet era, religion did not have much of an impact on tourism. Religious shrines were considered only as historically interesting and aesthetically attractive objects. For Catholics, the Holy Land is Israel, Catholic shrines are also located in Italy, the Vatican,

France, Portugal and other countries of Western Europe. Holy places for visiting Judaism are concentrated in Israel, Romania, the Czech Republic, Germany, Spain and Ukraine.

For followers of Islam - Sunnis, the holy cities are Mecca and Medina in Saudi Arabia. The places of pilgrimage for Shiites are primarily the cities of An-Najarf and Karbala in Iraq.

The main shrines of Buddhists are located in India, China and Tibet. The Russian region of Buddhism is defined by a datsan located near Ulan - Ude (Buryatia)

Pilgrimage is known to almost all modern religions. Its history goes back to ancient times. One of the first tourists, of course, were medieval pilgrims. Outstanding temples, sacred natural landscapes (mountains, groves) of the Far East, Central Asia, the Middle East, Ancient Greece attracted tens of thousands of people. The Greek historians Herodotus and Pausanias, the writer Lucian left us descriptions of the largest cult centers of antiquity. The oracle at Greek Delphi attracted the attention of famous people of antiquity who wanted to receive a prophecy regarding their fate.

Due to religious beliefs or curiosity about their own or someone else's faith, people all over the world travel to visit the Holy Land, the Vatican, Mecca, monasteries and other holy places. There are almost as many purposes of pilgrimage as there are pilgrims themselves. Pilgrimages have been and are being made to get rid of illness, to avoid misfortune, to atone for sin. Confessors often imposed penance, demanding to make a pilgrimage, and sometimes they ordered to go barefoot or in one shirt. Marco Polo (thirteenth century) mentions pilgrims he met in what is now Sri Lanka. Pilgrims from England in the XIV-XV centuries made their journeys mainly to Rome, Jerusalem. Often their travels were fraught with serious difficulties. Starting in 1388, English pilgrims, by order of King Richard II, were required to obtain and carry special permits, the prototype of today's passport. Eleven years later, Richard limited the number of ports from which English pilgrims were allowed to travel to distant lands to only two - Dover and Plymouth. Sailing from another port required special permission from the king himself.

The purpose of the pilgrimage is to fulfill the religious duty of the believers, to receive special grace for providing those difficulties that hinder the pilgrimage, as well as to participate in cult actions that are of the most blessed, sanctified nature.

The pilgrim wants to touch those places that were, as it were, consecrated by the founder of his religion and his closest followers in order to be filled with grace and partake of holiness. He participates in religious rites and ceremonies, receives instruction from the priests and monks who are in this holy place.

Sometimes a pilgrimage is performed in order to gain confidence in the correctness of an important decision made, in order to receive healing (bodily and mentally), in order to overcome a spiritual crisis or thank the deity for the recovery that has taken place. A pilgrimage can also have political goals if, by making it, a political figure acquires greater political weight. So, at the beginning of the 20th century, Nicholas II made a trip to Sarov, Nizhny Novgorod province, where the monastery of one of the most revered Russian saints, Seraphim of Sarov, is located. In July 1903, up to 500,000 pilgrims took part in the celebrations of the glorification of St. Seraphim of Sarov. And participation in this celebration of the Russian emperor strengthened people's faith in the closeness of the autocrat to the people and elevated his authority.

The immediate motive for the pilgrimage may be a personal conviction of the need to commune with grace and holiness, an example of fellow believers, a religious norm, or the advice of a clergyman.

Pilgrimage is in contact with educational tourism, but does not coincide with it. Here, acquaintance with a new country or city is strictly purposeful and necessary for the fulfillment of the religious duty of the believer. Often a pilgrim seeks to obtain new information about a country or places of worship only in order to expand their religious ideas. However, modern pilgrimage also has a significant cognitive aspect. Pilgrims, to one degree or another, get acquainted with the cult monuments of the country or city, as well as simultaneously with the culture and sights of the country as a whole. In addition, a modern pilgrim is often a person who travels only to touch religious shrines, to see places associated with the history of major religions, but not to take part in religious activities. Here, cognitive goals displace proper religious ones.

Pilgrimage presupposes a certain relation of a person to reality. The psychological characteristics of pilgrims are very diverse. A pilgrim in most cases is a deeply religious person with an already established system of values. He is ready for a while to give up his usual way of life: social circle, pleasures, food in order to achieve his spiritual and moral goals. The idea of a pilgrimage implies actions in the conditions of certain difficulties, voluntarily undertaken obligations to be in these conditions. This symbolizes the willingness of a person to sacrifice the temporal and transient material in the name of the eternal spiritual. In Hinduism, Orthodoxy and Catholicism, and other faiths, foot pilgrimages have developed, especially along already existing routes. People go on pilgrimages when ritual activities in places where they usually live are not enough for them. They travel or go to holy places that are more meaningful to them.

In science, several types of pilgrimage are usually distinguished, classified according to various criteria:

1) by the number of participants and family affiliation - individual, family and group pilgrimages;

2) by duration - long and short-term pilgrimages (previously, according to Russian Orthodox canons, a trip lasting more than 10 days was considered a pilgrimage);

3) by seasonality - year-round pilgrimages, as well as those dedicated to religious holidays;

4) according to the objects of visit - visits to confessional places of worship (churches, monasteries, temples), as well as natural places of worship (mountains, lakes, caves, springs, groves);

5) according to the location of the object of pilgrimage - internal (within state borders) and foreign pilgrimage tours;

6) on the basis of obligation - voluntary and mandatory pilgrimage tours (for example, in Islam, the Hajj pilgrimage is mandatory for every true believer).

Conclusion. Pilgrimage is an important ritual part of the activities of religious organizations, both Christians and Muslims, Jews and other confessions. In its essence, this is a ritual journey to a holy place, an object that contains all the signs of tourism activity, but in certain respects standing outside of it, outside the mass types of tourism accepted in secular society.

The pilgrimage made a great contribution to the development of travel. It greatly contributed to the spread of geographical knowledge, acquaintance with the culture of other peoples. Passing through many lands and countries, pilgrims brought in oral and, often in written form, legends, songs, stories. Pilgrims carried gifts and donations to the church, monasteries and the local population provided them with shelter and food.

The important role of the pilgrimage is defined as missionary and bringing enlightenment and strengthening the faith. At the heart of the pilgrimage lies precisely the love for the shrine. Orthodox go to shrines, looking for spiritual shelter and consolation. Many find a way out of a difficult state of mind in a pilgrimage.

In the process of solving the tasks set, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Pilgrimage is a journey or journey to holy places with well-defined cult purposes. The origin of pilgrimage is associated with the formation of major religious movements in the world.

Pilgrimage in one form or another is accepted in almost all religions and pagan cults. At present, pilgrims widely use the services of the tourism

industry. Pilgrimage tours, unlike religious-educational tours or cultural-historical tours, carry the meaning of performing a rite to certain beliefs, and not just educational goals.

Pilgrimage tourism is one of the oldest types of tourism. Pilgrimage, like tourism in general, is domestic (within a single country) and international.

The impact of religious tourism on the economy of some countries and regions of the world, primarily on the religious centers themselves, is very high. This is due to the fact that pilgrims leave a significant share of the money taken on the road in the camp. In addition, the pilgrimage provides income to many thousands of local residents. The centers of religious tourism are: Mecca, Medina, Jerusalem, the Vatican and other cities and areas.

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